

ISic2705

I.Sicily inscription 2705

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 46

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334802

1. Ἀφροδισία

2. Κλωδία

3. χαῖρε.

4. ²columba²

5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645125

PHI 334802

Bibliography

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Calderone, S. 1949. Analecta epigraphica liparensia. *Epigraphica*. 11: 49-60. At 51 no.1

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2705. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387293>